

1 **Supplementary Materials** for the article

2 **"Low-carbon MgO/hydromagnesite binders – Effect of moisture**
3 **state on the evolution of mechanical properties"**

4 by

5 **Ye Zhu^{a,b,1}, Alexander German^{a,b,1}, Mateusz Wyrzykowski^{a,2}, Nikolajs Toropovs^a,**
6 **Frank Winnefeld^a, Pietro Lura^{a,b}, Michele Griffa^{a,2}**

7 ^a *Empa, Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, CH-8600 Dübendorf, Switzer-*
8 *land*

9 ^b *Institute for Building Materials (IfB), ETH Zürich, CH-8093 Zürich, Switzerland*

¹ These authors contributed equally.

² Correspondence by E-Mail: M. Wyrzykowski (mateusz.wyrzykowski@empa.ch); M. Griffa (michele.griffa@empa.ch).

10 **S1. Longitudinal SIMO(N)RUS measurements. Implementation and** 11 **data analysis details**

12 **S1.1. SIMORUS measurements implementation**

13 Figure S 1 shows a block diagram representation of the longitudinal SIMORUS measurement implemen-
14 tation.

15 We used a periodic waveform generator (PWG) to drive, with a sinusoidal voltage at fixed amplitude,
16 fixed frequency and zero phase the (longitudinal) pin transducer acting as the point-like source of the
17 specimen's longitudinal vibrations. Our PWG is a NI PXI-5406 waveform generator. Its sinusoidal signal
18 was fed into a fixed-gain ($\times 50$) high voltage (HV) amplifier (model 2350 by TEGAM), bringing the signal's
19 amplitude to the wanted $5 V_{pp}$ level.

20 The specimen was vibrated for a total time of 40 ms. During the first 30 ms (ring-up time, $\Delta t_{ring-up}$), no
21 longitudinal vibration signal was acquired at the receiver's point on the specimen surface, in order to
22 wait for the vibration mode to achieve its steady state. After $\Delta t_{ring-up}$, the vibration signal was recorded
23 for a total duration of $\Delta t_{acq} = 10$ ms. We chose the $\Delta t_{ring-up}$ value based upon preliminary tests, aimed
24 at guaranteeing that the ring-up would be larger than or at least equal to 5 times the largest value of
25 the Q -factor of the excited first linear longitudinal vibration mode multiplied by the mode's period, ac-
26 cording with the suggestions by Ulrich and Le Bas [1].

27 The vibration signal was the Y -component of the surficial vibration particle velocity, $v_y(t)$, measured via
28 a single point laser Doppler vibrometer (LDV) manufactured by Polytec GmbH (laser head model Vi-
29 broFlex Neo VFX-I-110, equipped with a class 2 He-Ne (633 nm) laser beam and a VFX-O-SRS SR-objec-
30 tive, decoder model VibroFlex Connect VFX-F-110 with 24 MHz frequency bandwidth). $v_y(t)$ was meas-
31 ured with a LDV sensitivity $s = 2.5$ (mm/s)/V and a 100 kHz bandwidth. We chose, for each specimen,
32 the location where $v_y(t)$ was measured as, approximately, the center of the 40×40 mm² (X - Z) surface
33 opposite to the one in contact with the vibration source. To aim the LDV's beam at such location, the
34 LDV's head was mounted on a 2D moving stage consisting of the combination of two high precision
35 (100 nm minimum displacement)/high load linear stages (model M-414.3DG by PhysikInstrumente
36 GmbH & Co KG). At the measurement location on the specimen's surface, we glued a piece of reflective
37 tape (model A-RET-T050 by Polytec GmbH). We shone the LDV's beam at that location via a small win-
38 drow open through the glove box's door (see Figure 3(a) within the article). We remark that, despite the
39 presence of such open window, the glove box's atmosphere could be kept fluctuating, during the meas-
40 urements on all the specimens of the same group, in a narrow range about the wanted target value (57%
41 or 98%). This allowed minimizing the changes in the specimens' water saturation degree during the
42 measurements themselves. Indeed, we measured, between the beginning and the end of the measure-
43 ments, a mass relative change of the order of -0.1% and -1.13% , for the SIMORUS and SIMONRUS
44 measurements, respectively. We remind the reader that the SIMORUS measurements lasted significantly
45 less than the SIMONRUS ones.

46 The analog RF signal output from the LDV was digitized by a 14-bit depth NI PXIe-5122 digitizer at 20
47 MHz sampling frequency and with a dynamic range of $4 V_{pp}$.

48 After $\Delta t_{ring-up} + \Delta t_{acq}$ ms, the vibration drive and respective signal acquisition was repeated at the same
 49 drive amplitude but by increasing the drive frequency f_{exc} by a step $\Delta f_{exc} = 5$ Hz. Such procedure was
 50 repeated with f_{exc} varying within the (frequency sweep) interval [2;50] Hz. At each f_{exc} , the amplitude
 51 and phase of $v_y(t)$ were estimated online via a digital signal processing (DSP)-based heterodyne detec-
 52 tion procedure (see Section 7.1 in [2]) implemented within the Resonance Inspection Techniques & Anal-
 53 ysis (RITA) software platform, developed at the Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) [1]. The RITA
 54 software allowed also for the automation/control of the overall measurement protocol and for the esti-
 55 mation of the resonance frequency. In the latter case, we used the RITA's "parabolic peak fitting" module,
 56 which performs a parabolic fitting of the resonance curve within a moving window of a given size and
 57 locates the resonance peak at the respective parabola's maximum point inside the window where the
 58 two functions have maximum zero-lag cross-correlation value.

59 As shown in Figure 3 of the article, the specimens were suspended at their mid length via a pair of plastic
 60 holders. Under the assumption of stress-free boundary conditions, such prismatic specimens have a
 61 nodal region exactly at that location, when vibrating in their first longitudinal vibration mode.

62
 63
 64 *Figure S 1: block diagram representation of the SIMO(N)RUS measurements implementation. ① X-Z specimen sur-*
 65 *face where the longitudinal (Y-) vibration velocity signal, $v_y(t)$, was measured via the laser Doppler vibrometer (LDV)*
 66 *consisting of the laser head ③, mounted on the 2D stage ②, and of the decoder ④. ⑥ indicates a NI PXIe-1083*
 67 *chassis containing a periodic waveform generator (PWG) and a signal digitizer (DAQ), both controlled via a Thunder-*
 68 *bolt connection to a computer running the RITA software. The PWG fed the sinusoidal drive signal into the high volt-*
 69 *age (HV), fixed gain amplifier, whose output was fed to either the pin transducer (SIMORUS case) or the thickness*
 70 *mode, disk shaped transducer (SIMONRUS case) used as vibration source, in contact with the X-Z specimen surface*
 71 *opposite to the one where $v_y(t)$ was measured.*

72
 73

74 **S1.2 Repeatability of SIMORUS measurements**

75 We assessed the repeatability level of the longitudinal SIMORUS measurements by choosing, at each
 76 curing RH and for each specimen group, one specimen and by performing on it the spectroscopic
 77 measurement four times successively, every time by repositioning it on the specimen holder. We
 78 measured specimen size and mass before starting the first SIMORUS measurement. We performed two
 79 of them in a row. Then, we performed one SIMONRUS measurement. After it, we left the specimen
 80 within the glove box to relax back to its equilibrium (visco-elastic) state, following the high (strain) am-
 81 plitude drives during the SIMONRUS protocol. Finally, we performed the remaining, successive two SI-
 82 MORUS measurements.

83 All the measurements were performed at 57 days since casting, after the overall experimental cam-
 84 paign was concluded, and they involved the specimens 98 A, 98 D, 57 A and 57 D, where the label 98
 85 refers to the 98% RH specimen group, while the 57 one refers to the 57% RG group.

86 Each inset in Figure S 2 shows the four SIMORUS spectra obtained from the repeated measurements. It
 87 shows them within their full frequency ranges, within which resonance peaks other than the first longi-
 88 tudinal one (highlighted by the dashed rectangular box) also occurred. The small sub-inset inside each
 89 inset shows a zoom-in on the first longitudinal resonance peak. It allows resolving a bit better the res-
 90 onance peak position. It can be observed that, while the resonance peak position along the frequency
 91 axis did not vary a lot, the peak's amplitude varied significantly, as a consequence of the distinct reali-
 92 zations of the contact between the specimen and the pin transducer used as vibration source (see Fig-
 93 ure 3 c within the article).

94 Table S 1 provides, for each specimen, the average value and the range of the estimates of $E_{l,1}$ and α_ξ
 95 obtained from the four resonance peaks.

96

Specimen ID	Average $E_{l,1}$ [GPa]	$E_{l,1}$, range [GPa]	Average $\alpha_\xi \times 10^4$ [Np/mm]	$\alpha_\xi \times 10^4$, range [Np/mm]
98 A	17.233	0.307	1.877	0.195
98 D	21.870	0.084	1.471	0.082
57 A	42.610	0.066	0.472	0.029
57 D	42.885	0.127	0.482	0.025

97 *Table S 1: average value and range of values (i.e., maximum – minimum) of the four estimates of the dynamic, linear*
 98 *(storage) Young's modulus, $E_{l,1}$, and of the linear wave amplitude attenuation coefficient, α_ξ , obtained by the four*
 99 *SIMORUS measurements, repeated at the 57th day since casting.*

100

101

102 *Figure S 2: longitudinal SIMORUS spectra measured, for each specimen, at the end of the experimental campaign*
 103 *repeatedly and successively for 4 times, each time by repositioning the specimen on its holder, to evaluate the re-*
 104 *peatability level of such measurements. Insets a, b, c and d show the 4 spectra for the 98 A, 98 D, 57 A and 57 D*
 105 *specimens, respectively. In each inset, the curves in different colors refer to successively repeated measurements. The*
 106 *dashed rectangular region highlights the first order longitudinal resonance peak, which is also shown in the zoom-in*
 107 *sub-inset. Notice that more than one resonance peak was found within the frequency range the measurement was*
 108 *performed, some of those peaks being higher order longitudinal ones, i.e., harmonics of the first one.*

109

110 **S1.3. SIMONRUS measurements implementation**

111 Each resonance curve at a distinct drive amplitude was acquired with the same hardware and (RITA)
 112 software settings described above, except for

113 (1) the drive amplitude itself (as applied to the vibration source), which varied between 5 V_{pp} (value for
 114 the measurement in the almost-linear regime) and 400 V_{pp}, by increasing steps of 20 V_{pp} (measurements
 115 in the nonlinear regime),

116 (2) the drive frequency f_{exc} , which was swept within a narrow interval containing the first longitudinal
 117 resonance frequency at any drive amplitude and with a finer increasing step $\Delta f_{exc} = 1$ Hz,

118 (3) the LDV sensitivity, which was fixed for any drive amplitude and needed to be coarser ($s = 25$
 119 (mm/s)/V) in order to allow a higher vibration velocity dynamic range and

120 (4) $\Delta t_{ring-up}$, which was optimized for each specimen to approximately satisfy the condition $\Delta t_{ring-up} \geq$
 121 $5 \frac{Q_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0}$, where $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$ indicates the 1st order longitudinal resonance frequency measured in correspondence
 122 of the chosen first drive amplitude (5 V_{pp}) and $Q_{l,1}^0$ is the Q -factor of the corresponding resonance peak.

123 At each drive amplitude, we estimated the resonance frequency and resonance vibration velocity ampli-
 124 tude data, $(f_{l,1}; V_{l,1})$, using the same "parabolic peak fitting" module implemented in RITA and adopted
 125 for the analysis of the SIMORUS measurements. We then converted the longitudinal vibration velocity
 126 amplitude, $V_{l,1}$, values into the corresponding longitudinal strain amplitude ones, $\Delta\varepsilon$, according with the
 127 relation $\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{V_{l,1}}{2Lf_{l,1}}$, obtainable from the expression of the stationary (longitudinal strain) wave function
 128 of the first longitudinal vibration mode, evaluated on the plane $y = L$ and under the assumption of
 129 stress-free boundary conditions [3].

130 As mentioned in Section 2.3.2 of the article and shown in Figure 3(d) there, we substituted the pin trans-
 131 ducer, used as vibration source in the SIMORUS measurements, with a thickness-mode piezoelectric disk
 132 glued to the same X - Z surface which the pin transducer was in contact with. Such transducer is made of
 133 a piezoelectric ceramics (lead zirconate-titanate, PZT), has thickness of 6.97 ± 0.05 mm and diameter of
 134 28 ± 0.38 mm and is manufactured by APC International Ltd. (material type PZT855, falling within the
 135 USA Navy Class V for PZTs, according to the MIL-STD-1367b(SH) standard [4]). The glue consisted of
 136 Salol (phenyl salicylate, $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$, by SigmaAldrich). Phenyl salicylate becomes liquid when heated above
 137 43 °C (315 °K) but it re-crystallizes fast at room temperature [5,6]. When crystallized, it provides a hard
 138 bonding between the transducer and the specimen's surface. However, given a high crystallinity degree,
 139 it is rather brittle under shear deformation, allowing for an easy transducer detachment.

140 Each specimen was associated with a distinct transducer, used at any point in the measurement time
 141 series, to increase the repeatability of the vibration source strain imposed on the specimen.

142

143 **S1.4. SIMONRUS data: statistical models, slow dynamics assessment and infer-** 144 **ence of the elastic nonlinearity type**

145 Depending upon which nonlinear terms are considered in the stress-strain constitutive equation (Eq. (6)
 146 within the article), different relationships between the relative change in the (1st order) longitudinal res-
 147 onance frequency, $\frac{f_{l,1}(\Delta\varepsilon) - f_{l,1}^0}{f_{l,1}^0}$, and the longitudinal strain amplitude, $\Delta\varepsilon$, can be obtained. If only the first
 148 two nonlinear terms in Eq. (6) are considered (i.e., the terms with β and δ as parameters coupling the
 149 longitudinal stress, σ , to the 2nd and 3rd order powers, respectively, of the instantaneous longitudinal
 150 strain, ε), then the relationship assumes the following quadratic form [3]

151

$$\frac{f_{l,1}(\Delta\varepsilon) - f_{l,1}^0}{f_{l,1}^0} \propto \delta \Delta\varepsilon^2 \quad (S1)$$

152 instead of the linear form shown in Eq. (7) within the article. Such linear form is obtained from Eq. (6) by
 153 considering only the nonlinear mesoscopic elasticity term in α_f [7,8]. The expression in Eq. (S1) is typical
 154 of materials exhibiting mostly a classical nonlinear elastic behavior, while the expression of Eq. (7) in the
 155 article is the one typical of materials exhibiting mostly a mesoscopic nonlinear elastic behavior.

156 In this Section, we address in detail two issues concerning the statistical modeling of our SIMONRUS
 157 ($\Delta\varepsilon; f_{i,1}$) datasets (also called SIMONRUS scatter plot datasets).

158 First, we motivate the choice of adding one regression parameter, c , as a constant, to either the quadratic
 159 relationship expressed by Eq. (S1) or the linear relationship expressed by Eq. (7) within the article. We
 160 show below how such choice relies upon the assumption of not being able to exclude a (weak) nonlinear
 161 elastic response of our specimens when driven to resonance by the smallest drive amplitude we used.
 162 Such assumption stems from the fact that we performed initial, test SIMONRUS measurements by vary-
 163 ing the drive amplitude within a small interval about the mentioned linear range value of $5 V_{pp}$. Within
 164 such measurements, we did not detect any corresponding resonance frequency shift. Such result could
 165 be due indeed to a fully linear elastic behavior of the specimens in the corresponding small strain range.
 166 However, it could also be due to our specific measurement configuration. For example, the resonance
 167 frequency shift might have simply been smaller than the drive frequency step $\Delta f_{exc} = 1$ Hz used to build
 168 up the resonance curves. Such an uncertainty is typical in any SIMONRUS measurement.

169 Second, we motivate the preference for the linear regression model of Eq. (7) than for the quadratic one
 170 of Eq. (S1), thus assuming a purely mesoscopic nonlinear elastic behavior for our specimens, based upon
 171 (1) magnitude of the regression (in-sample) error, i.e., how well the regression model could fit the data,
 172 and (2) assessment of the magnitude of slow dynamics effects, which are characteristic features of
 173 mesoscopic nonlinear elasticity.

174 Concerning the first issue, we assign the following names to the following variables,
 175

$$\tilde{y} \equiv f_{i,1}(\Delta\varepsilon) - f_{i,1}^0 \quad (S2)$$

$$x \equiv \Delta\varepsilon \quad (S3)$$

$$\tilde{Y} \equiv \frac{\tilde{y}}{f_{i,1}^0} \quad (S4)$$

176
 177 where \tilde{Y} simply renames the relative change in resonance frequency computed with respect to the res-
 178 onance frequency, $f_{i,1}^0$, achieved at a drive amplitude (assumed unknown), in correspondence of which
 179 the specimen still exhibits a purely linear elastic response.

180 Both Eq. (7) within the article and Eq. (S1) above can be generically expressed as
 181

$$\tilde{Y} = ax^b \quad (S5)$$

182
 183 where b is either equal to 1 (mesoscopic nonlinear case, Eq. (7)) or to 2 (classical, cubic nonlinearity case,
 184 Eq. (S1)). Equation (S5) is the general model for the relationship between relative change in resonance
 185 frequency and strain amplitude, as derived from distinct models of the nonlinear stress-strain constitu-
 186 tive relationship (Eq. (6) within the article).

187 Under the assumption made, we do not measure $f_{l,1}^0$, rather $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$, the resonance frequency in corre-
 188 spondence of our lowest drive amplitude (5 V_{pp}), independently of whether the specimen may or may
 189 not respond weakly nonlinearly at such drive amplitude. Thus, our measured relative changes in reso-
 190 nance frequency are not the actual \tilde{Y} rather

191

$$\hat{Y} \equiv \frac{f_{l,1}(\Delta\varepsilon) - \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} = \frac{\hat{y}}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} \quad (S6).$$

192

193 We observe that one can write \hat{y} also as

194

$$\hat{y} \equiv f_{l,1}(\Delta\varepsilon) - \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0 = f_{l,1}(\Delta\varepsilon) - f_{l,1}^0 - (\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0 - f_{l,1}^0) = \tilde{y} - (\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0 - f_{l,1}^0) \quad (S7)$$

195

196 Thus, by combining Eqs. (S6) and (S7) with (S4) and (S5), one can express what we actually measured,
 197 i.e., \hat{Y} , as

198

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{f_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} \tilde{Y} + \frac{f_{l,1}^0 - \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} = \frac{f_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} a x^b + c = a' x^b + c \quad (S8)$$

199

200 where a' and c simply summarize the following quantities,

201

$$a' = \frac{f_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} a \quad (S9)$$

$$c = \frac{f_{l,1}^0 - \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} \quad (S10)$$

202

203 Equation (S8) simply indicates that, under the assumption made and under the additional hypothesis of
 204 validity of Eq. (S5), the regression of SIMONRUS data should be performed according with such modified
 205 model, whose regression parameters a' and c relate with the actual nonlinear elasticity parameter a . This
 206 latter parameter can be derived by combining Eqs. (S9) and (S10) together:

207

$$a = \frac{1}{1+c} a' \quad (S11).$$

208

209 In the pure mesoscopic nonlinear elasticity case ($b = 1$ and $a = \alpha_f$ in Eq. (S5)), Eq. (S5) + Eq. (S11) cor-
 210 responds to Eq. (7) within the article.

211 From Eq. (S10), we notice that the regression parameter c allows estimating the relative difference be-
 212 tween the resonance frequency in the pure linear elastic regime and the one we measured at the lowest
 213 drive amplitude.

214 Concerning the choice between the mesoscopic and the classical, cubic elastic nonlinearity types of
 215 $(\Delta\varepsilon; f_{i,1})$ relationship, we performed first a physics-agnostic and purely statistical assessment of the re-
 216 gression results. Specifically, we computed, at each time point and for each specimen, the values of the
 217 following 3 goodness-of-fit (GoF) indexes, for the regression results obtained with either regression
 218 model:

219

$$SSE = \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Y}_i - \tilde{a}'x_i^b - \tilde{c})^2 \quad (S12)$$

(Sum of Squared Errors)

$$RMSE \equiv \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \cdot SSE} \quad (S13)$$

(Root Mean Squared Error)

$$DOF - adjusted R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{N-1}{N-p}\right) \frac{SSE}{SST} \quad (S14)$$

(Degrees Of Freedom-adjusted coefficient of determination).

220 In Eqs. (S12), (S13) and (S14), $(x_i; \hat{Y}_i)_{i=1, \dots, N}$ are the collected experimental SIMONRUS data, according to
 221 the definitions in Eqs. (S3) and (S6). N is the total number of drive amplitudes, excluding the smallest
 222 one. $p = 2$ is the total number of regression parameters, $SST \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Y}_i - \langle \hat{Y} \rangle)^2$ and $\langle \hat{Y} \rangle \equiv \frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{Y}_i$,
 223 while \tilde{a}' and \tilde{c} are the optimal estimates of the regression parameters and b was, in our case, equal ei-
 224 ther to 1 or to 2, depending on the regression model used. The latter optimal estimates were obtained
 225 by using, also in the $b = 1$ (i.e., mesoscopic nonlinearity) case, the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm [9]
 226 for solving nonlinear least-squares problems, as implemented in the built-in function `fitt(...)` of Matlab
 227 [10], R2020b Update 4.

228 Figure S3(a) showcases an example of SIMONRUS spectra obtained, at 1 day of curing, from one speci-
 229 men belonging to the 98% RH group. It shows a decrease in $f_{i,1}$ with increasing drive amplitude. Figure
 230 S4(b) shows the corresponding linear regression results (red line) for the $(x_i; \hat{Y}_i)_{i=1, \dots, N}$ data (blue circles)
 231 of Figure S5(a).

Figure S 6: An example of Single MOde Nonlinear Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy (SIMONRUS) results (obtained for one specimen of the 98% RH group, at 1 day of curing). (a) The raw SIMONRUS spectrum, where the dark resonance curves were obtained in correspondence of increasing drive amplitudes, while the blue ones (at the bottom of the figure, see also the zooming-in window) were obtained by repeating the measurement at the smallest drive amplitude; any blue curve followed a corresponding black one; the red crosses indicate the identified resonance peak, leading to the dataset $(\Delta\varepsilon; f_{i,1})_i$, with the index i enumerating the increasing drive amplitudes. $\Delta\varepsilon$ indicates the longitudinal strain amplitude, expressed in micro-strains ($\mu\varepsilon$). (b) The SIMONRUS scatter plot. The circles, showing the relative change of $f_{i,1}$ (black curves in (a)) with respect to the previously measured $\tilde{f}_{1,1}^0$ (blue curve a), $\frac{\Delta f_{1,1}}{\tilde{f}_{1,1}^0}$, as a function of $\Delta\varepsilon$. The solid red line shows the results of the data regression according to Eq. S15. The estimated regression parameters, including the rescaled slope (Eq. S16) are provided as well as the values of 3 goodness-of-fit metrics (degrees of freedom-adjusted R^2 , root mean squared error, $RMSE$, and sum of squared errors, SSE).

232

233

234 Figure S7 shows, in each row, the values of one of the 3 goodness-of-fit indexes, the left column referring
 235 to the linear regression (mesoscopic nonlinearity, $b = 1$) case, the right column to the quadratic (cubic,
 236 classical nonlinearity, $b = 2$) one. In terms of DOF-adjusted R^2 values, the linear model performed
 237 slightly better (values closer to 1) than the quadratic one, especially for the datasets within the first 14
 238 days. The quadratic model also bore larger SSE (thus also $RMSE$) values at 7 and 14 days, for the 98%
 239 RH-cured specimens.

240 The qualitative patterns in nonlinear Young's modulus evolution with time and respective differences
 241 for the distinct specimen groups do not change if one considers, instead of the absolute value of the
 242 mesoscopic nonlinear Young's modulus $|\alpha_f|$ (Figure 8 within the article), the absolute value of the cu-
 243 bic, classical nonlinear Young's modulus $|\delta|$ estimated by the quadratic regression mentioned above.
 244 Figure S 3 a shows the temporal evolution of the estimated $|\delta|$ while Figure S 3 b shows its relative
 245 change with respect to its value at 1 day (first time point). We notice that we mean here by δ the full
 246 proportionality coefficient between \tilde{Y} (see Eq. (S4)) and $x^2 = \varepsilon^2$, according to Eq. (S5) with $b = 2$, ob-
 247 tained after the rescaling according with Eq. (S11). Such proportionality coefficient is a rescaled version
 248 of the actual δ appearing in Eq. (6) within the article, with the scaling coefficient being a constant (see
 249 Eq. 3.66 in [3]).

250 Similarly for $|\alpha_f|$, $|\delta|$ increased dramatically till about 14 days for the 98% RH-cured specimens, after
 251 which it slightly decreased towards, supposedly, a plateau value. The 57% RH-cured specimens exhib-
 252 ited only a monotonic decrease. Experimental groups' specimens always showed higher elastic nonlin-
 253 earity values than the control groups' ones, very likely as a consequence of the quasi-static loading
 254 they were subjected to for measuring the quasi-static, linear Young's modulus, before the nonlinear
 255 one was measured.

256
 257 *Figure S 8: goodness-of-fit indexes for evaluating, at any time point and for any specimen undergoing SIMONRUS*
 258 *measurements, the quality level of the regression of the SIMONRUS data (resonance frequency relative change versus*
 259 *longitudinal strain amplitude) according to two distinct models. Insets a, c and e: linear regression model of Eq. S17*
 260 *with $b=1$ (including the constant c as additional regression parameter), suggested by the mesoscopic elastic nonline-*
 261 *arity theory. Insets b, d and f: quadratic regression model of Eq. S18 with $b=2$ (also in this case including the constant*

262 *c* as additional regression parameter), suggested by the classical, cubic elastic nonlinearity theory. See Eqs. (S12),
 263 (S13) and (S14) for the definition of the distinct indexes. For each RH value (98% or 57%), the specimens labeled as A
 264 to C were those subjected to the quasi-static loading (referred to as "loaded" within the article). The specimens la-
 265 beled as D to F were those not subjected to the quasi-static loading (referred to as "control" within the article).

266

267

268 *Figure S 9: a) evolution of the cubic, classical nonlinear Young's modulus (absolute value thereof), $|\delta|$, with curing*
 269 *time, with a zoom-in on the smaller values of the 57% RH groups' specimens and of the 98% RH ones at the first*
 270 *point in the time series (right column in the inset). Distinct markers refer to the distinct specimen groups. Each*
 271 *marker shows the average of three values measured for three distinct specimens of the same group. Each error bar*
 272 *shows the full range of the three measured values. b): same time series as in inset a but by reporting on the vertical*
 273 *axis the relative change in $|\delta|$ with respect to its value at 1 day. For each RH value (98% or 57%), the specimens la-*
 274 *beled as A to C were those subjected to the quasi-static loading (referred to as "loaded" within the article). The speci-*
 275 *mens labeled as D to F were those not subjected to the quasi-static loading (referred to as "control" within the arti-*
 276 *cle).*

277 In addition to the purely statistical evidence of slightly better performance of the linear regression model
 278 than the quadratic one, the SIMONRUS implementation according to the Pasqualini-Hauptert protocol
 279 [11,12] allowed us assessing whether the specimens exhibited slow dynamics effects or not and, if they
 280 did, how strong such effects were.

281 The term slow dynamics is an "umbrella term" for distinct types of long-lasting nonlinear elastic re-
 282 sponses of the material to a change in dynamic strain amplitude, from an infinitesimal strain level to one
 283 large enough to induce a nonlinear elastic response. Such long-lasting responses cannot be explained
 284 based upon the classical theory of nonlinear elasticity. For example, the 1D nonlinear stress-strain con-
 285 stitutive relation of Eq. (6) within the article entails a unique functional dependence of the effective

286 Young's modulus, $\hat{E}_l(\varepsilon)$, from the strain amplitude ε , if Eq. (6)'s mesoscopic nonlinear term in α_f is dis-
 287 regarded. In such a case, for a given value ε , \hat{E}_l has a unique value. Therefore, when switching suddenly,
 288 during a sinusoidal drive, from a very small drive (thus strain) amplitude to a much larger one, the cor-
 289 responding resonance frequency would drop to a smaller value simultaneously to the drive amplitude
 290 switch. That would happen because a jump in ε would imply a jump in \hat{E}_l , thus in (longitudinal) reso-
 291 nance frequency $f_{l,1}$. Correspondingly, the opposite would occur if the drive amplitude was suddenly
 292 switched from a very large to a very small value: a simultaneous jump upwards in resonance frequency
 293 would occur.

294 On the contrary, materials exhibiting mesoscopic nonlinear behavior, thus better described by the form
 295 of Eq. (6) including the term in α_f , do not respond only with a single drop in resonance frequency to a
 296 jump upwards in strain amplitude: if such strain amplitude is sustained, the resonance frequency, after
 297 the sudden drop, continues to slowly decrease towards a plateau (so called conditioning effect) [13,14].
 298 Symmetrically, when transitioning suddenly from a large to a very small and sustained strain amplitude,
 299 the resonance frequency jumps immediately upwards and, additionally, slowly relaxes towards an as-
 300 ymptotic value (relaxation effect) [13,14]. Such long-lasting continuations towards asymptotic values
 301 indicate that the material's elastic state does not depend only on the current strain value, rather also on
 302 its previous history, as it can be also evinced from the $sign(\dot{\varepsilon})$ term in Eq. (6) within the article.

303 During a SIMONRUS measurement, the specimen's elastic state is quantified by the resonance frequency
 304 value. The latter is identified via a frequency sweep, as in any continuous wave (CW) spectroscopic
 305 method. During the whole frequency sweep at fixed drive amplitude, the specimen's strain amplitude
 306 varies while the drive frequency approaches/departs from the resonance one. Such strain amplitude
 307 variation, during the single resonance curve build-up, introduces both conditioning (left side of the res-
 308 onance peak) and relaxation (right side of the peak) effects. That is especially the case when the specimen
 309 is driven at amplitudes large enough to stimulate vigorous nonlinear elastic responses. However, since
 310 both conditioning and relaxation typically occur at rather long time scales (from several minutes to about
 311 an hour [13,15–20]) compared with the data acquisition time for a single resonance curve, the specimen
 312 has typically not enough time to achieve an equilibrium state, i.e., an asymptotic \hat{E}_l value. As a conse-
 313 quence, the lack of equilibrium makes it difficult to compare, e.g., across distinct material types or same
 314 materials but in distinct nonlinear mesoscopic elastic states (in our case, at distinct curing times), the
 315 distinct elastic states themselves: in different states, the quantification may be less or more biased by
 316 how much out-of-equilibrium the material is, which in turns depends upon eventual differences in the
 317 strength of slow dynamics effects.

318 In order to assess slow dynamics effects' presence and strength, Pasqualini *et al.* [11] proposed to probe
 319 the specimen's current linear elastic state, after a nonlinearity-induced drive during SIMONRUS, by build-
 320 ing up a single resonance frequency curve, at the lowest drive amplitude adopted in the chosen protocol,
 321 immediately after the build-up of each resonance curve at high (i.e., nonlinearity-inducing) drive ampli-
 322 tude. This implies that, during the protocol, not only a single $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$ value is measured, rather a series,
 323 $\{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0\}_{i=0,\dots,N-1}$, again with N indicating the total number of nonlinearity-inducing amplitudes. The
 324 stronger the slow dynamics effects, the larger the difference between the current linear elastic state (i.e.,

325 linear resonance frequency, $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$) and the one assessed at the very beginning of the measurement (i.e.,
326 resonance frequency obtained by the very first resonance curve, $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$). Pasqualini *et al.* used such mod-
327 ified SIMONRUS protocol only to assess at which large drive amplitude (thus strain amplitude level) their
328 specimens started to exhibit, remarkably, slow dynamics (thus mesoscopic nonlinearity) fingerprints.
329 Hauptert *et al.* went further by proposing in [12] to exploit such modified protocol for compensating for
330 slow dynamics effects, by computing the resonance frequency relative change of Eq. (7) in the article, at
331 the $(i + 1)$ -th nonlinearity-inducing amplitude, not based upon the $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$ value, rather upon the one
332 measured during the previous resonance curve build-up at the lowest drive amplitude, i.e., $\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0$. We
333 remark that such compensation is only partial, since during the build-up time of a single resonance curve
334 a complicated mixture of conditioning and relaxation effects likely occur without, in either case, to allow
335 for sufficient time for achieving respective equilibria. SIMONRUS, as a nonlinear elasticity measurement
336 approach, intrinsically cannot allow for a complete uncoupling of conditioning and relaxation effects
337 during its execution [14,21,22], a limitation referred as an "observer effect" in [23].
338 In addition to following the protocol proposed by Hauptert *et al.* for implementing SIMONRUS, we were
339 inspired by the approach chosen by Pasqualini *et al.* in addressing the task of assessing qualitatively the
340 slow dynamics presence and strength for fingerprinting the presence of mesoscopic nonlinearity. We
341 propose doing that by computing

342

$$\frac{|\Delta \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0|}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0} \equiv \frac{|\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0 - \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0|}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0}, \forall i = 1, \dots, N \quad (S19)$$

343

344 and by plotting it vs the corresponding longitudinal resonance strain amplitude, $\Delta \varepsilon$, value achieved in
345 correspondence of the i -th nonlinearity-inducing drive amplitude, i.e., the same values plotted on the
346 horizontal axis in Fig. S10. Equation (S15) expresses a relative change in the resonance frequency meas-
347 ured at the lowest drive amplitude (i.e., "linear resonance frequency") as a consequence of a drive at a
348 nonlinearity-inducing drive amplitude.

349 Figure S11 shows such scatter plots for each of the 4 specimen groups (distinct insets) and at each
350 measurement time point (distinct markers). With the exception of the 98% control group (inset b), all
351 specimens exhibited, within the first two days since casting, evidence of slow dynamics with similar
352 strength, with a relative change in linear resonance frequency at the scale of 1 part per mil. Thus, even
353 at such very early age, the type of nonlinear elastic behavior could be considered as of mesoscopic type.
354 At later time points, the specimens exposed to the two distinct RH values still exhibited evidence of
355 mesoscopic elastic nonlinearity but with opposite trends with time: the slow dynamics strength increase
356 with time for the specimens at 98% RH, while it decreased for those at 57%. The latter result correlates
357 well with the increase and decrease in $|\alpha_f|$, respectively, although a slight decrease, followed by a plat-
358 eauing, for the 98% specimens and after 14 days is not clearly observable, in terms of slow dynamics
359 strength. On the contrary, such slight decrease is unequivocal for $|\alpha_f|$ (see Figure 8 within the article).

360

361

362

363

364

365

366

367

368

Figure S 12: scatter plots of the relative change in linear resonance frequency, $\frac{|\Delta \tilde{f}_{l,1}^0|}{\tilde{f}_{l,1}^0}$, as a function of the resonance vibration strain amplitude, $\Delta\varepsilon$, achieved at the preceding nonlinearity-inducing drive amplitude. Each inset refers to a different specimen group: a), experimental group at 98% RH; b), control group at 98% RH; c), experimental group at 57% RH; d), control group at 57% RH. Different datasets, indicated by distinct markers, refer to distinct curing time points (day 1 to day 56, d1 to d56, respectively). Each data point and its error bar shows the average and the range of the respective values from the three specimens of the respective group, as measured in correspondence of one nonlinearity-inducing drive amplitude.

369 **S2. X-ray tomography analysis. Implementation details and addi-** 370 **tional results.**

371 **S2.1 Measurement settings**

372 We performed X-ray tomography with an EasyTomo XL-Ultra instrument manufactured by RX Solu-
373 tions (Chavanod, France). Such instrument consists of a reflection-based, micro-focus X-ray source and
374 a flat panel X-ray detector. The X-ray source is a Hamamatsu L10801. The emitted X-ray beam has a
375 conical geometry, with a 30° opening angle, and can achieve a maximum photon energy of 230 keV.
376 The X-ray detector is manufactured by Varian and consists of a 2D array of amorphous Si pixels (1920
377 × 1536), each with physical size $p = 127 \mu\text{m}$, covered with a thin layer of CsI (scintillator for the X-ray
378 photons). For our specific measurements, we set the source's acceleration voltage to 160 kV (corre-
379 sponding X-ray photon energy up to 160 keV) and the current to 170 μA . In such range, Compton
380 scattering and photoelectric absorption are the two most probable physical processes of interaction
381 between X-ray photons and atoms. Thus, each tomogram's voxel value is a proxy variable of the X-ray
382 attenuation coefficient, μ (units of length^{-1}). μ is proportional to (1) a power of the local, effective
383 atomic number, Z_{eff} , and to (2) the local mass density, ρ . Thus, within the mentioned X-ray photon en-
384 ergy, larger voxel values are associated with denser portions of the specimen. The specimen-to-source
385 distance (d_{ss}) was 141.14 mm and the source-to-detector distance (d_{sd}) was 551.43 mm. The geomet-
386 rical magnification achieved in the 2D raw projections (so-called "radiographs") thus was $M \equiv$
387 $\frac{d_{sd}}{d_{ss}} \cong 3.907$. The resulting effective voxel size for the final tomograms was $\tilde{p} = \frac{p}{M} \cong 32.5 \mu\text{m}$. We remind
388 that this is not the actual spatial resolution of the tomograms, as 3D images. Their actual (effective)
389 spatial resolution is of the order of double the values of \tilde{p} (upper bound), because of convolutions of
390 multiple point spread functions of different components of the image formation process, e.g., blurring
391 by the X-ray source finite size. We estimated the latter, for the set voltage and current levels men-
392 tioned above, based upon the X-ray source's manufacturer technical specifications.

393 As mentioned already within the article, we conducted tomography only for the middle region along
394 the longitudinal (Y) direction (see Fig. 3 within the article) of each specimen, covering a volume of in-
395 terest (VOI) of $59.75 \times 43.45 \times 59.74 \text{ mm}^3$ (X , Y and Z axes, respectively, full specimen size = $40 \times 40 \times 160$
396 mm^3). The rotation axis of the specimen stage was approximately parallel to the specimens' longitudi-
397 nal direction, i.e., the Y axis. For each tomography, we acquired 4800 radiographs over 360° of speci-
398 men rotation. Each acquired radiograph was the results of pixel-wise averaging of 20 radiographs at
399 the same rotation angle. Each single radiograph for the averaging was obtained by exposing the X-ray
400 detector for $\approx 85 \text{ ms}$ to the X-ray beam. We performed the tomographic reconstruction by using a
401 GPU-optimized cone beam filtered back-projection algorithm [25] provided by RX Solutions (XACT
402 software, Ver. 1.1). We saved each tomogram as a stack of 2D 16 bit unsigned integer TIFF images.
403 Since each reconstructed tomogram has voxel values originally in 32 bit float format, saving each of
404 them with a 16 bit unsigned integer digitization, while still maintaining voxel value comparability
405 across tomograms, at each time point, required fixing, for each of them, the same range of 32 bit float
406 voxel values to be mapped to 16 bit unsigned integer interval. The 32 bit float range was [0.15;4.5].

407 Each 2D image, called "tomographic slice", is a 2D digital cross-section of the volume "tomograph-
408 ically" reconstructed and, in our case, it was approximately orthogonal to the longitudinal direction of
409 the specimen. The slices were equidistant from each other, i.e., the voxels were isotropic, with inter-
410 slice distance equal to the voxel size \tilde{p} .

411 **S2.2 3D rigid body registration**

412 As mentioned in Section 2.3.4 of the article, the qualitative comparison of the three, time-lapse tomo-
413 grams of any given specimen required, first, to align each of them to a reference one, which we chose
414 to be the tomogram at 1 day. The misalignment, at 7 and 28 days, stemmed from the limitations in the
415 accuracy with which any specimen could be set always at the same position on the tomograph's rota-
416 tion stage, at the distinct measurement time points. Such accuracy was smaller than the tomographic
417 spatial resolution of about 65 μm . Thus, at 7 and 28 days, a specific portion within the tomographed
418 region, was displaced compared with at 1 day. We remark that the mentioned misalignment was not the
419 only source of displacement. The specimens were at 7 and 28 days deformed, compared with their
420 states at 1 day, due to the ongoing shrinkage or expansion. However, we tried to compensate only for
421 the component of the total displacement due to the misalignment. We achieved that by applying to
422 the tomograms at 7 and 28 days a 3D rigid body registration [26] procedure implemented by using the
423 Python API of elastix [27,28], made available in SimpleElastix [29]. "Rigid body" means that the as-
424 sumed mathematical form of the displacement vector field, $\vec{u}(\vec{x})$, was the one describing a rotation fol-
425 lowed by a translation, i.e.,

426

$$427 \quad \vec{u}(\vec{x}) = (\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{1}_3)\vec{x} + \vec{a} \quad (\text{S1})$$

428

429 where \mathbf{R} is a 3×3 , real-valued orthogonal matrix with determinant = 1 expressing the transformation of
430 a 3D rotation, $\mathbf{1}_3$ is the 3×3 identity matrix and $\vec{a} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is a 3×1 real-valued column vector expressing
431 the transformation of a 3D translation.

432 An example of a Python script implementing such 3D rigid body registration by using the SimpleElastix
433 API is the following, used for registering the 7-day tomogram to the 1-day one for the 57 A specimen:

434

```
435 #!/usr/bin/env python3  
436 # -*- coding: utf-8 -*-  
437 """
```

```
438 Python script to perform a rigid body registration of two tomograms of the  
439 MgO/HY mortars series, investigated within the LHUS project.
```

```
440 The registration is performed with the SimpleElastix library, which is just  
441 a set of wrappers, in distinct programming languages, to the C/C++ elastix  
442 library.
```

```
443 The deformation model is a simple rigid body one ("Euler transformation" in  
444 elastix jargon): a translation + a rotation.
```

```

445 Reference tomogram ("fixed image", in elastix jargon):
446 MgOHY_57RH_Spec_A_1Day
447 Tomogram to be registered ("moving image"): MgOHY_57RH_Spec_A_7Days
448
449 @author: Ye Zhu
450 Concrete and Asphalt Laboratory
451 Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (Empa)
452 ETH Domain
453 Ueberlandstrasse 129, CH-8600, Duebendorf (ZH), Switzerland
454 E-mail: ye.zhu@empa.ch
455 Created on Oct. 30th 2022
456 Last modified on: Nov. 1st 2022.
457 """
458 import SimpleITK as sitk
459 #####
460 #
461 # Define directory/file paths or names
462
463 # Full path to the output directory folder, where the log files and the
464 # registration's output files should be written
465 outDir = "/mnt/storage1/zhye/LHUS/MgOHY_Mortars/RigidBodyRegistra-
466 tion_57RH_Spec_A/f1Day_m7Days"
467 # Full path of the TIFF file of the fixed (i.e., reference) image
468 fixImage = "/mnt/storage1/zhye/LHUS/MgOHY_Mor-
469 tars/MgOHY_57RH_Spec_A_1Day/SlicesY_rotated_3_cropped_to_ROI.tif"
470 # Full path of the TIFF file of the moving (i.e., to be registered) image
471 movImage = "/mnt/storage1/zhye/LHUS/MgOHY_Mor-
472 tars/MgOHY_57RH_Spec_A_7Days/SlicesY_rotated_minus_3_cropped_to_ROI.tif"
473 # Full path of the parameters map file
474 paramMapFile = "/mnt/storage1/zhye/LHUS/MgOHY_Mortars/RigidBodyRegistra-
475 tion_57RH_Spec_A/f1Day_m7Days/Parameters_RigidBody.txt"
476 # Name of the TIFF file where the registered moving image should be saved
477 registMovImageFilename = "MgOHY_57RH_Spec_A_7Days_RGRegistr_to_1Day.tif"
478 #####
479 # Estimate the optimal transformation vector field needed for the
480 # registration
481
482 elastixImageFilter = sitk.ElastixImageFilter()
483 elastixImageFilter.LogToConsoleOn()
484 elastixImageFilter.SetOutputDirectory(outDir)
485 elastixImageFilter.SetFixedImage(sitk.ReadImage(fixImage))

```

```

486  elastixImageFilter.SetMovingImage(sitk.ReadImage(movImage))
487  parameterMapVector = sitk.VectorOfParameterMap()
488  parameterMapVector.append(elastixImageFilter.ReadParameterFile(pa-
489  ramMapFile))
490  print(parameterMapVector)
491  elastixImageFilter.SetParameterMap(parameterMapVector)
492  elastixImageFilter.Execute()
493
494  elastixImageFilter.GetParameterMap()
495  transformParameterMap = elastixImageFilter.GetTransformParameterMap()
496  #####
497  # Apply the estimated optimal transformation vector field to the moving
498  # image to register it to the fixed one
499
500  transformix = sitk.TransformixImageFilter()
501  transformix.SetOutputDirectory(outDir)
502  transformix.LogToConsoleOn()
503  transformix.SetTransformParameterMap(transformParameterMap)
504  transformix.ComputeDeformationFieldOn()
505  transformix.SetMovingImage(sitk.ReadImage(movImage))
506  transformix.Execute()
507  transformix.GetComputeDeformationField()
508  resultFloatImage = transformix.GetResultImage()
509  sitk.WriteImage(resultFloatImage, registMovImageFilename)
510  #####
511
512  The SimpleElastix parameters map file mentioned within that Python script (see the variable pa-
513  ramMapFile) contains the input parameters for the different elastix's functions called by the registra-
514  tion workflow, thus defines its settings. The content of such input text files is reported here below and
515  was the same for the registration of any couple of tomograms:
516
517  (FixedInternalImagePixelType "short")
518  (FixedImageDimension 3)
519  (MovingInternalImagePixelType "short")
520  (MovingImageDimension 3)
521  (Registration "MultiResolutionRegistration")
522  (Interpolator "LinearInterpolator")
523  (ResampleInterpolator "FinalBSplineInterpolator")
524  (Resampler "DefaultResampler")

```

```
525 (FixedImagePyramid "FixedRecursiveImagePyramid")
526 (MovingImagePyramid "MovingRecursiveImagePyramid")
527 (Optimizer "AdaptiveStochasticGradientDescent")
528 (Transform "EulerTransform")
529 (Metric "AdvancedMattesMutualInformation")
530 (AutomaticScalesEstimation "true")
531 (AutomaticTransformInitialization "true")
532 (HowToCombineTransforms "Compose")
533 (NumberOfHistogramBins 64)
534 (ErodeMask "false")
535 (NumberOfResolutions 5)
536 (MaximumNumberOfIterations 1000)
537 (NumberOfSpatialSamples 20000)
538 (ImageSampler "RandomCoordinate")
539 (NewSamplesEveryIteration "true")
540 (BSplineInterpolationOrder 1)
541 (FinalBSplineInterpolationOrder 3)
542 (DefaultPixelValue 0)
543 (WriteResultImage "true")
544 (ResultImagePixelFormat "short")
545 (ResultImageFormat "mhd")
```

546

547 **S2.3 Segmentation of solid phases voxels**

548 We developed a 3D image processing workflow for classifying each voxel of any tomogram as belong-
549 ing or not to the specimen's solid phases (i.e., aggregates or binder paste), a classification task also
550 called as "binary segmentation" in the image analysis and computer vision fields. We implemented
551 such workflow with the "Segment Phases 3D" plugin for ImageJ [30–32], belonging to Beat Münch's
552 Xlib collection of ImageJ plugins [33]. In order to simplify the explanation of each workflow step, we
553 show in Figure S13, as an example, the output of each step for a specific tomogram (the one at 1 day)
554 of one specimen (57 A).

555 The workflow consisted of the following steps:

556

- 557 1. the empty space surrounding the specimen's volume (see the dark regions at the boundaries of
558 the image field in Figure S14(a)) was segmented using the specific type of seeded region growing
559 [34] algorithm implemented in the "Segment Phases 3D" plugin, with a spatial constraint of 5
560 voxels and the region growing from one single seed point within the set of voxels with values in
561 the interval [0;25000], corresponding to voxels where air was present; this binary segmentation re-
562 sulted in a binary tomogram, i.e., a 8-bit unsigned integer tomogram with voxels having either of

563 only two possible values, 0 or 255, with 0 (or black on a screen) indicating a voxel not belonging to
564 the sought class (specimen's volume surrounding space, in this case), while 255 (or white on a
565 screen) indicating belonging to the class; see Figure S15(b) for such a binary tomogram in the case
566 of the 1-day tomogram of specimen 57 A;

567

568 2. we applied a Boolean NOT operator ("NOT" button in the "Segment Phases 3D" plugin) to the bi-
569 nary tomogram of step 1, producing a new one (Figure S16(c)), indicating voxels located inside the
570 specimen's volume;

571

572 3. we segmented the pore space by a procedure consisting of the following sub-steps:

573

574 3.1. selecting all the voxels, independently of their position, with values in the interval [0;25000]
575 ("Lower Threshold" = 0 and "Upper Threshold" = 25000 in "Segment Phases 3D") and creat-
576 ing a respective binary tomogram for air regions (either outside of the specimen's volume or
577 pore space ones);

578

579 3.2. applying to the binary tomogram produced by 3.1 a morphological erosion operator ("Erode"
580 button) with structural element equal to a sphere with diameter of 2 voxels ("Parameter" field
581 set to 2);

582

583 3.3. performing a Boolean AND operation ("AND" button) between the binary tomogram gener-
584 ated by 3.2 and the one generated at step 2, in order to create a binary tomogram consider-
585 ing only pore space voxels;

586

587 3.4. applying to the binary tomogram output by 3.3 a morphological dilation operator ("Dilate"
588 button) with structural element equal to a sphere with diameter of 4 voxels ("Parameter" field
589 set to 4); the output of this sub-step is a refined binary tomogram of the pore space, exempli-
590 fied in Figure S17(d); such segmented pore space consisted mainly of air voids and a few po-
591 rous patches;

592

593 4. we then applied the Boolean NOT operator to the final output from step 3, to select any region
594 which was not part of the specimen's pore space (see the binary tomogram in Figure S18(e));

595

596 5. finally, we performed the Boolean AND operation between the binary tomogram obtained at step
597 4 and the one obtained at step 2, thus creating a new binary tomogram (Figure S19(f)) for the
598 voxels satisfying two conditions, i.e., (1) not belonging to the pore space and (2) located within the
599 specimen's volume; thus such voxels are those where solid phases (either aggregates or binder)
600 are present.

601
 602 *Figure S 20: showcase of the output from each step of the 3D image processing workflow for segmenting the speci-*
 603 *men's volume but with the exclusion of air voids, as applied to the tomogram at 1 day of the 57 A specimen. (a): ver-*
 604 *tical cross-section from the tomogram at 1 day, as also shown in Figure 13 a within the article. (b): vertical cross-*
 605 *section at the same position as in in (a) but of the binary tomogram of the segmented space surrounding the speci-*
 606 *men's volume (white parts at the image's boundaries). (c): corresponding vertical cross-section from the binary tomo-*
 607 *gram of the segmented specimen's volume, complementary to the tomogram shown in (b). (d): corresponding verti-*
 608 *cal cross-section from the binary tomogram of the segmented air voids. (e): corresponding vertical cross-section from*
 609 *the binary tomogram complementary to the one shown in (d). (e): vertical cross-section from the binary tomogram of*
 610 *the specimen's volume with air voids excluded, obtained from the Boolean AND operation between the tomogram in*
 611 *(c) and the one in (e).*

612
 613 The binary tomogram, output at the end of the workflow and indicating which voxels belonged to the
 614 specimen's solid phases, acted then as a sort of label map for the Matlab function collecting the values
 615 of the solid phases' voxels in a single set, interpreted as a statistical *ensemble* of a random variable (the
 616 voxel value itself), and estimating that variable's probability density function (PDF) from such *ensemble*
 617 of its realizations.

618
 619 **S2.4 Comparison of time-lapse tomograms**

620 We provide in Figure S21, Figure S22, Figure S23 and Figure S24 examples, additional to those pro-
 621 vided by Figure 9 within the article, of the lack of significant, qualitative differences between the X-ray
 622 tomograms at the distinct time points, for the 57 A, 98 B, 57 D and 98 D specimens, respectively. See
 623 Section 3.5 within the article for further explanations.

624

625 *Figure S 25: 2D cross-sections from three time-lapse X-ray tomograms of the 57 A specimen, each cross-section located at the same position inside the specimen's volume. Each cross-*
 626 *section is parallel to the XY plane indicated in the frame of reference in Figure 4 of the article. a): tomogram at 1 day. b): tomogram at 7 days. c): tomogram at 28 days. The tomograms*
 627 *at 7 and 28 days (insets b and c) were registered according to a rigid body (i.e., rotation + translation) deformation model to the respective tomograms at 1 day (inset a, in order to*
 628 *compensate for any possible specimen misalignment at the two distinct measurement time point, thus to allow for the cross-section at the same exact position, taken from the tomo-*
 629 *grams at the two time points, to show the same portion of the volume. Brighter voxels indicate higher local X-ray attenuation, mainly born by the sand grain, while darker ones indicate*
 630 *lower local X-ray attenuation (cement paste and air voids, in order of decreasing voxel value).*

631

632

633

634

635
636
637
638
639
640
641
642
643

Figure S 26: analogous figure as Figure S27 except for the specimen 98 B. a): tomogram at 1 day. b): tomogram at 7 days. c): tomogram at 28 days.

644

645

Figure S 28: analogous figure as Figure S29 except for the specimen 57 D. a): tomogram at 1 day. b): tomogram at 7 days. c): tomogram at 28 days.

646

647

648

649

650

651

652

653

654
655
656
657
658
659
660
661

Figure S 30: analogous figure as Figure S31 except for the specimen 98 D. a): tomogram at 1 day. b): tomogram at 7 days. c): tomogram at 28 days.

662 **References**

663 [1] T.J. Ulrich, P.-Y. Le Bas, Resonance Inspection Techniques & Analyses (RITA). Version 3.0.3.18.
 664 User guide., (2019).

665 [2] A. Migliori, J.L. Sarrao, Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy. Applications to Physics, Materials
 666 Measurements, and Nondestructive Evaluation, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, New York, NY, USA,
 667 1997.

668 [3] R.A. Guyer, P.A. Johnson, Chapter 3. Traditional Theory of Nonlinear Elasticity, Results., in: Nonlin-
 669 ear Mesoscopic Elast., Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, Germany, 2009.
 670 <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527628261>.

671 [4] USA Dept. of Defense (DoD), Military Standard. Piezoelectric Ceramic Materials and Measure-
 672 ments Guidelines for Sonar Transducers, MIL-STD-1376B(SH), USA Dept. of Defense (DoD), Ar-
 673 lington (VA), USA, 1995.

674 [5] B. Capon, B.Ch. Ghosh, The mechanism of the hydrolysis of phenyl salicylate and catechol mono-
 675 benzoate in the presence and absence of borate ions, *J. Chem. Soc. B Phys. Org.* (1966) 472–478.
 676 <https://doi.org/10.1039/J29660000472>.

677 [6] R.B. Hammond, M.J. Jones, K.J. Roberts, H. Kutzke, H. Klapper, A structural study of polymorphism
 678 in phenyl salicylate: determination of the crystal structure of a meta-stable phase from X-ray
 679 powder diffraction data using a direct space systematic search method, *217 (2002) 484–491*.
 680 <https://doi.org/10.1524/zkri.217.9.484.22887>.

681 [7] R.A. Guyer, K.R. McCall, G.N. Boitnott, Hysteresis, Discrete Memory, and Nonlinear Wave Propa-
 682 gation in Rock: A New Paradigm, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 74 (1995) 3491–3494.
 683 <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.74.3491>.

684 [8] R.A. Guyer, P.A. Johnson, Chapter 6. Hysteretic Elastic Elements., in: Nonlinear Mesoscopic Elast.,
 685 Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, Germany, 2009.
 686 <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527628261>.

687 [9] W.H. Press, S.A. Teukolsky, W.T. Vetterling, B.P. Flannery, Chapter 15: Modeling of Data. Section
 688 15.5: Nonlinear Models. Sub-section 15.5.2: Levenberg-Marquardt Method, in: *Numer. Recipes*
 689 *Art Sci. Comput.*, 3rd edition, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 2007: pp. 801–805.
 690 <http://numerical.recipes/book/book.html>.

691 [10] The MathWorks Inc., MATLAB R2020b Update 4, (2020).

692 [11] D. Pasqualini, K. Heitmann, J.A. TenCate, S. Habib, D. Higdon, P.A. Johnson, Nonequilibrium and
 693 nonlinear dynamics in Berea and Fontainebleau sandstones: Low-strain regime, *J. Geophys. Res.*
 694 112 (2007) B01204. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JB004264>.

695 [12] S. Hauptert, G. Renaud, J. Rivière, M. Talmant, P.A. Johnson, P. Laugier, High-accuracy acoustic de-
 696 tection of nonclassical component of material nonlinearity, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 130 (2011) 2654–
 697 2661. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.3641405>.

698 [13] J.A. TenCate, Slow Dynamics of Earth Materials: An Experimental Overview, *Pure Appl. Geophys.*
 699 168 (2011) 2211–2219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00024-011-0268-4>.

700 [14] M. Scalerandi, C. Mechri, M. Bentahar, A. Di Bella, A.S. Gliozzi, M. Tortello, Experimental Evidence
 701 of Correlations Between Conditioning and Relaxation in Hysteretic Elastic Media, *Phys. Rev. Appl.*
 702 12 (2019) 044002. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.12.044002>.

703 [15] J.A. TenCate, E. Smith, R.A. Guyer, Universal Slow Dynamics in Granular Solids, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 85
 704 (2000) 1020–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.85.1020>.

705 [16] M. Bentahar, H. El Aqra, R. El Guerjouma, M. Griffa, M. Scalerandi, Hysteretic elasticity in damaged
 706 concrete: Quantitative analysis of slow and fast dynamics, *Phys. Rev. B.* 73 (2006) 014116.
 707 <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.73.014116>.

- 708 [17] N. Tremblay, E. Larose, V. Rossetto, Probing slow dynamics of consolidated granular multicompo-
709 site materials by diffuse acoustic wave spectroscopy, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 127 (2010) 1239–1243.
710 <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.3294553>.
- 711 [18] A.S. Kodjo, P. Rivard, F. Cohen-Tenoudji, J.-L. Gallias, Impact of the alkali–silica reaction products
712 on slow dynamics behavior of concrete, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 41 (2011) 422–428.
713 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2011.01.011>.
- 714 [19] P. Shokouhi, J. Rivière, R.A. Guyer, P.A. Johnson, Slow dynamics of consolidated granular systems:
715 Multi-scale relaxation, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 111 (2017) 251604. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5010043>.
- 716 [20] M. Bentahar, A. Di Bella, C. Mechri, S. Montresor, M. Scalerandi, X. Yu, Exploiting Slow Dynamics
717 Effects for Damage Detection in Concrete, *Front. Built Environ.* 6 (2020) 64.
718 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2020.00064>.
- 719 [21] M. Scalerandi, C. Mechri, M. Bentahar, A. Di Bella, A.S. Gliozzi, M. Tortello, Role of slow dynamics
720 in fast dynamics ultrasonic measurements, *Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul.* 91 (2020)
721 105452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnsns.2020.105452>.
- 722 [22] A. Carriá, Effects of slow dynamics and conditioning on non-linear hysteretic material assessment
723 using impact resonance acoustic spectroscopy, *Mech. Syst. Signal Process.* (2021) 15.
- 724 [23] J.A. TenCate, P.A. Johnson, Chapter 2. Nonlinear Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy: Assessing
725 Global Damage, in: *Nonlinear Ultrason. Vibro-Acoust. Tech. Nondestruct. Eval.*, Springer Nature
726 Switzerland AG, Cham (Switzerland), 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-94476-0>.
- 727 [24] C. Di Bella, M. Griffa, T.J. Ulrich, P. Lura, Early-age elastic properties of cement-based materials as
728 a function of decreasing moisture content, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 89 (2016) 87–96.
729 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2016.08.001>.
- 730 [25] L.A. Feldkamp, L.C. Davis, J.W. Kress, Practical cone-beam algorithm, *JOSA A.* 1 (1984) 612–619.
- 731 [26] B. Zitová, J. Flusser, Image registration methods: a survey, *Image Vis. Comput.* 21 (2003) 977–
732 1000. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0262-8856\(03\)00137-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0262-8856(03)00137-9).
- 733 [27] S. Klein, M. Staring, K. Murphy, M.A. Viergever, J. Pluim, elastix: A Toolbox for Intensity-Based
734 Medical Image Registration, *IEEE Trans. Med. Imaging.* 29 (2010) 196–205.
735 <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2009.2035616>.
- 736 [28] D. Shamonin, Fast parallel image registration on CPU and GPU for diagnostic classification of Alz-
737 heimer’s disease, *Front. Neuroinformatics.* 7 (2014) 50/1–15.
738 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2013.00050>.
- 739 [29] K. Marstal, F. Berendsen, M. Staring, S. Klein, SimpleElastix: A User-Friendly, Multi-lingual Library
740 for Medical Image Registration, in: *2016 IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. Workshop*
741 *CVPRW*, IEEE, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016: pp. 134–142. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPRW.2016.78>.
- 742 [30] C.A. Schneider, W.S. Rasband, K.W. Eliceiri, NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis, *Nat.*
743 *Methods.* 9 (2012) 671–675. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2089>.
- 744 [31] J. Schindelin, I. Arganda-Carreras, E. Frise, V. Kaynig, M. Longair, T. Pietzsch, S. Preibisch, C.
745 Rueden, S. Saalfeld, B. Schmid, J.-Y. Tinevez, D.J. White, V. Hartenstein, K. Eliceiri, P. Tomancak, A.
746 Cardona, Fiji: an open-source platform for biological-image analysis, *Nat. Methods.* 9 (2012) 676–
747 682. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2019>.
- 748 [32] C.T. Rueden, J. Schindelin, M.C. Hiner, B.E. DeZonia, A.E. Walter, E.T. Arena, K.W. Eliceiri, ImageJ2:
749 ImageJ for the next generation of scientific image data, *BMC Bioinformatics.* 18 (2017) 529.
750 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-017-1934-z>.
- 751 [33] B. Münch, Beat Münch’s Xlib library of ImageJ plugins, Xlib. (2015). <https://imagej.net/Xlib>.
- 752 [34] R. Adams, L. Bischof, Seeded Region Growing, *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* 16 (1994)
753 641–647.

754
755